

Method Development and Validation of Rosuvastatin in bulk drug Formulation and Stress Degradation Studies by UV

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Abstract

A simple, accurate, precise, and sensitive UV spectrophotometric method was developed for the determination of Rosuvastatin Calcium in bulk form. The optimum conditions for the analysis of the drug were established. Rosuvastatin Calcium was subjected to stress degradation under different conditions recommended by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH). The samples so generated were used for forced degradation studies using the developed method. The solvent used is ammonium acetate buffer and acetonitrile (30:70) the wavelength corresponding to maximum absorbance of the drug was found at 242 nm. Beers law was observed in the concentration range of 2-12 µg/ml with correlation coefficient 0.996. The linear regression equation obtained by least square regression method were $y=0.0191X-0.0063$, where y is the absorbance and x is the concentration of the pure drug solution. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) for estimation of Rosuvastatin Calcium were 0.769306 µg/ml and 2.331231 µg/ml respectively. The method was validated for several parameters like accuracy, precision as per ICH guidelines. The values of relative standard deviation and % recovery were found to be satisfactory, indicating that the proposed method is precise and accurate and hence can be used for the routine analysis of Rosuvastatin Calcium in bulk form.

Keywords: Rosuvastatin Calcium; UV Spectroscopy; Validation; Assay

Introduction

Rosuvastatin calcium is used as an antihyperlipidemic, which is a HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor, a rate-limiting enzyme in cholesterol biosynthesis. It is used in the treatment of dyslipidemia, which is effective at low doses and its half-life is more compared to other statins. Chemically it is, calcium salt of (3R,5S,6e)-7-(4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-6-(1-methylethyl)-2-(ethyl (methylsulfonyl) amino)-5-pyrimidinyl)-3,5-dihydroxy-6-heptenoic acid (Figure 1) and molecular formula is $(C_{22}H_{27}FN_3O_6S)_2Ca$ [1]. Extensive literature survey reveals that a few spectrometric [2-9] were available for the estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium in bulk and formulations. The objective of the present study is to develop a new simple, sensitive, accurate, rapid and economic method for the estimation of Rosuvastatin Calcium in bulk and tablet formulation.

Literature survey reveals that only an LC-MS study has been reported for the quantification of Rosuvastatin Calcium in human plasma. some UV spectrophotometric method has been reported for the estimation of Rosuvastatin Calcium. The objective of the present work was to develop a simple, sensitive, precise, and accurate UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of Rosuvastatin Calcium in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations as per ICH Guidelines (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Structure of Rosuvastatin.

Materials And Methods

Instruments

A Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV1800, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) was used for all absorbance measurements with matched quartz cells.

Chemicals and Reagents

All chemicals acetonitrile, ammonium acetate and reagents were of analytical grade. Rosuvastatin Calcium in the form of powder with certificate of analysis was provided by Cipla Research Centre, Mumbai. Pharmaceutical grade excipients were obtained from Pharmaceutical Technology Lab. of Maharashtra.

Observation and results:

Determination of maximum wavelength (λ_{max})

Standard stock solution of 100 µg/ml of Rosuvastatin Calcium was prepared in mobile phase (10,11). From the above stock solution, pipette out 1 ml in to 10ml volumetric flask and finally made up the volume with mobile phase to produce a concentration of 10µg/ml. The samples were then scanned in UV spectrophotometer from a range of 200-400nm against mobile phase as blank and the wavelength corresponding to maximum absorbance in methanol was found at 242 nm (Figure 2).

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Figure 2: UV Spectrum of Rosuvastatin Calcium.

Preparation of standard calibration curve:

For the preparation of standard calibration curve, use stock of 100µg/ml concentration and 2-12 µg/ml concentration were prepared for analyzing calibration curve by pipetting out 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 ml from the stock solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and made up the volume with mobile phase . The absorbance of each solution was measured at 242 nm as blank. Calibration curve of the drug was then plotted by taking the absorbance obtained on y-axis and the concentration of the solution on x-axis (Figure 3).

Validation:

Validation can be defined as (ICH) Establishing documented evidence, which provides a high degree of assurance that a specific activity will consistently produce a desired result or product meeting its predetermined specifications and quality characteristics.

The method was validated for several parameters like linearity, accuracy, precision, Ruggedness, Robustness, Limit of detection (LOD), and Limit of quantification (LOQ) according to ICH guidelines.

Linearity

The linearity of the analytical method was its ability to elicit test results which are directly proportional to analyte concentration in samples within a given range. To establish the linearity of the proposed method, various aliquots of the standard solution of the drug were prepared from stock solution and analyzed. The drug showed linearity in the range of 2-12µg/ with correlation coefficient 1. Linearity data are shown in (Table 1).

Accuracy

This study was carried out using the stock solution (100µg/ml). Take three concentrations 2µg/ml, 6µg/ml, and 12µg/ml. And take six reading of these concentrations. The result was reported as %RSD. The accuracy result showed a good with percent relative standard deviation less than 2. A result shows that the method is accurate up to 12µg/ml.

Precision

Precision studies were carried out to ascertain the reproducibility

Figure 3: Calibration Curve of Rosuvastatin.

Table 1: Linearity table of Rosuvastatin Calcium.

Concentration µg/ml	Absorbance
2	0.047
4	0.08
6	0.124
8	0.155
10	0.193
12	0.24

Table 2: Linear regression data for calibration curve.

Parameters	Data
Range	2-12 µg/ml
Correlation coefficient	0.996
Slop	0.0191
Intercept	0.004429

of the proposed method. Repeatability was determined by preparing six replicates of same concentration of the sample and the absorbance was measured.

Intraday precision study was carried out by preparing drug solution of same concentration and analyzing it at three different times in a day. The same procedure was followed for one day to determine interday precision.

The result was reported as %RSD. The precision result showed a good reproducibility with percent relative standard deviation less than 2. The result shows that the method was found to be precise (Table 2).

Robustness

Analysis was carried out at two different wavelengths to determine the robustness of the method and the respective absorbance was measured. The result was indicated as %RSD which is less than 2%. The results shows that the method is robust for change in wavelength.

LOQ and LOD

Limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest amount of analyte in the sample that can be detected. Limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest amount of analyte in the sample that can be quantitatively determined by suitable precision and accuracy. The values of LOQ and LOD were found to be 0.769306 and 2.331231 µg/ml respectively.

Degradation studies

The ICH guidelinesQ1A (R2) entitled stability testing of new drug substances and products that required stress testing to be carried out to elucidate the inherent stability characteristics of the active substance.

The aim of this study was to perform the stress degradation studies on Rosuvastatin Calcium using the developed method (12).

Stress degradation by hydrolysis under acidic condition

The preparation of 0.01N hydrochloric acid (HCl) was done by diluting 0.085 ml of conc. HCl to 100 ml of distilled water. Amount of drug was weighed and was transferred to a labeled round bottomed flask. Refluxed the sample for 2 hrs and pipette out 1ml to 10 ml volumetric flask, made up the volume with mobile phase to get the final dilution so as to get final test concentration. Taken the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug (Table 3).

Stress degradation by hydrolysis under alkaline condition

The 0.01N Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) was prepared by dissolving 0.04 gm of sodium hydroxide pellets in 100 ml of distilled water. Amount of drug was weighed and was transferred to a labeled round bottom flask. Reflux the sample for 2 hrs and pipette out 1ml to 10 ml volumetric flask, made up the volume with diluent to get the final dilution to get final test concentration to get the final test concentration 10ppm. Take the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug.

Stress degradation by neutral condition

Amount of drug was weighed and transferred in to 100 ml water in round bottom flask. Reflux it for 2 hours. Pipette out 1ml in to 10 ml volumetric flask, made up the volume with diluent to get the final dilution to get final test concentration 10ppm. Take the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug.

Photolytic degradation

Photo stability was performed by placing amount of drug in daylight for 24 hours. The samples were diluted with mobile phase up to 10ml in a volumetric flask. Pipette out 1ml sample diluted up to 10 ml by diluent to get the final dilution to get final test concentration 10ppm. Take the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug.

Dry heat induced degradation

Standard drug was placed in an oven at 60°C for 2 hours to study dry heat degradation. Amount of drug samples were diluted with mobile phase up to 100ml in a volumetric flask. Pipette out 1 ml and were diluted up to 10 ml by diluent to get the final dilution so as to get final test concentration 10ppm. Take the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug.

Oxidative degradation

Weight accurately amounts of drug and transfer into 10 ml of volumetric flask which containing 3% hydrogen peroxide. Keep it in dark place for 2 hours. Pipette out 1 ml sample diluted up to 10 ml by diluent to get the final dilution to get final test concentration 10ppm. Take the reading on UV. Check the degradation behavior of drug.

Conclusion

The proposed UV method is simple, accurate, precise, specific and highly sensitive. The method is economical rapid and do not require any sophisticated apparatus in contrast to spectroscopic methods. The proposed method is also useful for the determination of rosuvastatin calcium stability in samples of pharmaceutical dosage forms. Hence,

Table 3: % Degradation under stress conditions.

Stress condition	% Degradation	Remark
0.01N HCl	58.21%	Unstable
0.01N NaOH	12.30%	Stable
Water	30.03%	Unstable
Dry Heat	29.20%	Unstable
Photolytic	23.23%	Unstable
H ₂ O ₂	28.28%	Unstable

the proposed method can be successfully used for routine quality control analysis of drug in marketed preparations.

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